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more information:

<https://copr.space-and-place.net/representation/a-sign-at-heidelberg-main-station-representing-heidelberg-as-a-city-of-science/v1/>

A sign at Heidelberg Main Station representing Heidelberg as a city of science

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The City of Heidelberg is located on the Neckar River and home to more than 150,000 residents. After initial settlement activities, Heidelberg was primarily inhabited as a royal seat from the 13th century onwards. Since then, it has developed into a modern city characterized by inventiveness, research, and science, a large student population, tourism, and historical heritage. Its old town and castle ruins make it a popular destination for both domestic and foreign tourists, especially from North America.

Besides being a tourist destination and a historical place, Heidelberg is home to a larger number of academic institutions. Among these is Heidelberg University, which was founded in 1386 as one of the oldest universities in Europe. It is renowned for its vibrant academic environment and is one of Germany's few universities of excellence, highly regarded worldwide. Alongside the university, Heidelberg hosts numerous internationally recognized research institutes, teaching institutions, and the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities.

A sign reading 'Heidelberg Hbf' is attached to a pole at Heidelberg Main Station. The name 'Heidelberg' was introduced in 1196 and has been used ever since to refer to the place that has developed into the city we know today. The sign displays the name in the same way as other place names on corresponding signs at other stations, including the prefix 'Hbf' (translates to 'main station'), thus making the people arriving at Heidelberg Main Station recognize it as quoting the name of the place and thus know that they have arrived in Heidelberg. The sign thus is a representation of the place.

Above the 'Heidelberg Hbf' sign, there is a smaller sign reading 'City of Science'. Unlike the former sign, which was installed for regular station operations, the latter was installed much later, in 2023, to highlight the scientific activities taking place in the city. The term 'City of Science' refers to a city that is distinguished by its contributions to science. Viewed in isolation, it does not refer to Heidelberg specifically but to a city in general. As both signs are, however, installed in combination, they jointly refer to Heidelberg and its longstanding research traditions. As these research traditions are not mentioned in the context of corresponding institutions but in relation to the city as a whole, they are imputed to the latter. Thus, Heidelberg is portrayed as a city that, in its entirety, is understood as being characterized by scientific research. This, in turn, is in the interests of the City of Heidelberg, which is shaping and communicating its identity in this way.

Literature

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